

CONCEPTUAL FOUNDATIONS OF A NEUROLINGUISTIC APPROACH TO MOTHER TONGUE AND READING LITERACY EDUCATION

Togayeva Umida Shavki kizi

Department of Primary Education,
Bukhara State University senior teacher,
pedagogical sciences Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)
u.s.togaeva@buxdu.uz
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Abstract: this article expresses current issues of methods of teaching the native language based on the neurolinguistic approach, the possibility of developing educational tasks from the native language based on the neurolinguistic approach, and the features of using best practices in the educational process.

Key words: neurolinguistics, neurolinguistic approach, creative thinking, reading, writing, listening, speaking, traditional education, independent thinking.

The organization of educational activities in new modern forms and methods, the ability to purposefully manage students in the course of the lesson, is considered the main criterion of teaching activity. The use of modern types and forms of lessons based on advanced pedagogical technology means determining the student's place in the educational process, providing a new approach to it, providing a new attitude, managing this process with skill and understanding. The purpose of conducting competition lessons in native language classes is to test the knowledge of the student in the language class, to be able to use the possibilities of the language in the process of mutual discussion and communication, to assess the level of speech skills, quick and clear thinking, and the ability to get out of problematic situations.

In the years of independence, the issue of the content, purpose and method of education in the mother tongue was put on the agenda and resolved. The educational content consists of a series of theoretical knowledge derived from the nature of the mother tongue. The purpose of education was "to improve students' oral and written speech, to form the ability to correctly express the product of thought in oral and written forms in accordance with the conditions of speech." The educational method has changed from reproductive (retelling) to cognitive-pragmatic (independent and creative thinking and expressing it according to speech conditions). This can be evaluated as an unprecedented event in the history of mother tongue education.

Neurolinguistics is a new branch of linguistics that studies the relationship between language and the structure and function of the brain. It appeared to meet the needs of clinical diagnostic tasks. Its purpose is to observe and control the use of the patient's speech style (interview, graphic, narrative, reading, writing, etc.). For neurolinguistics, observing the speech and behavior of people with brain damage while learning two or more languages is a very important issue.

The main part. Neurolinguistics historically emerged in the 19th century in the age of aphasiology, the study of linguistic deficits (aphasias) caused by brain damage. Aphasiology attempts to link structure to function by analyzing the effects of brain injuries on language processing. One of the first to make the connection between a specific brain area and language processing was the French surgeon Paul Broca, who performed autopsies on many people with speech impairments, and most of them were in the left frontal lobe. discovered brain damage in what is now known as Broca's area.

The term neurolinguistics is credited to Edith Crowell Trager, Henry Hecaen, and Alexander Luria in the late 1940s and 1950s. Luria's book, *Problems in Neurolinguistics*, is probably the first book on neurolinguistics. Harry Whitaker popularized neurolinguistics in the United States in the 1970s, founding the journal *Brain and Language* in 1974.

Although aphasiology is the historical core of neurolinguistics, the field has expanded significantly in recent years, in part because of new brain imaging technologies and the advent of time-sensitive electrophysiological techniques that emphasize brain activation when humans perform a variety of language tasks, particularly , in 1980, with the discovery of the N400, which is sensitive to semantic problems in language comprehension, electrophysiological techniques emerged as a viable method for language learning. The N400 was the first language-related brain response to be identified, and since its discovery, EEG and MEG have been increasingly used to conduct language studies.

Neurolinguistics is closely related to the field of psycholinguistics, which seeks to elucidate the cognitive mechanisms of language by applying traditional methods of experimental psychology; today, psycholinguistic and neurolinguistic theories often inform each other, and there is much collaboration between the two fields.

The method of teaching the mother tongue in primary grades is the first stage of the method of teaching the mother tongue in upper grades, and it teaches the students of the primary grade practically (accordingly) the issues it

examines. At the same time, there are specific features of the native language teaching methodology in primary classes. Teaching the mother tongue in primary grades includes not only grammar, spelling and related speech development methods, but also methods of reading and writing in the classroom and outside the classroom. Based on this, the science of mother tongue teaching methodology in primary grades performs the following tasks:

a) determining and justifying the content, size and existing system of the native language course in primary grades, that is, the program of the course (literacy, reading, grammar, spelling, speech development, etc.);

b) to study the process of formation of knowledge and skills from reading and writing, as well as the difficulties faced by students in this process, to analyze the cause of mistakes, to develop types of work that help to prevent and correct them;

d) students' clear understanding and thorough assimilation of the educational material given in their mother tongue, the ability to apply the knowledge they have acquired in practice and the general development of students, that is, their intelligence, memory, observation, memory, logical thinking, development of methods and tools that help to develop creative thinking and speech;

e) implementation of educational tasks set before schools in connection with teaching the mother tongue, formation of moral and aesthetic qualities in students.

The importance of the neurolinguistic approach is high in primary education mother tongue education. Because it is necessary to take into account the psychological and physiological characteristics of a primary school student. It is especially appropriate to use the neurolinguistic approach when creating educational tasks related to stories. For example, in the 4th grade reading textbook, Mary Joslin's story "The Pearl" can be taught through creative tasks to develop critical thinking skills. Answers to the following questions are sought in 2 stages:

Stage 1	Stage 2
1. Why was Robin not happy even though he was rich?	1. Why did the girl say that the pearl was really Josh's?
2. Why did Roben want to return to the place where he was born and raised?	2. Why did Josh tell Reuben that he could have the pearl?
3. Why do you think the name of the	3. How did Reuben's life change after

story is "Pearl"?	receiving the pearl? Explain with examples.
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In order to find answers to these questions, the reader first makes a deep observation about the events in the story. He thinks critically by answering questions, answers based on his psychology.

Much work in neurolinguistics involves testing and evaluating theories advanced by psycholinguists and theoretical linguists. In general, theoretical linguists propose models to explain the structure of language and how linguistic information is organized, psycholinguists propose models and algorithms to explain how linguistic information is processed in the mind, and neurolinguists analyze brain activity to determine what biological structures are.

The use of neurolinguistic approach in teaching native language to primary school students develops students' independent thinking skills and plays an important role in forming critical thinking skills.

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